

Growth and yield attributes of rice cultivars under deep water conditions. Cuttack, India, 1988.

Variety	Cross	Flowering date (DE) ^a	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
IET10084	Bashpair/Pankaj	31 Oct (159)	201	70	4.41	25.6	3.2	11.0
IET10030	Velki/Mahsuri	4 Nov (163)	197	83	3.20	25.8	3.0	8.5
IET10029	Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2	2 Nov (161)	196	75	3.44	26.4	3.0	8.7
IET10008	CN644/Patnai 23	31 Oct (159)	187	100	3.25	26.2	3.1	8.5
IET10003	Jaladhi 2/CN644	3 Nov (162)	193	70	3.82	26.7	3.0	8.5
IET10028	Jaladhi/Pankaj	1 Nov (160)	197	104	3.55	26.9	2.5	10.0
IET10009	CN644/Patnai 23	28 Oct (156)	190	75	3.00	26.6	2.2	7.7
IET9018	Selection from tall composite	1 Nov (160)	187	66	3.34	26.1	2.1	9.2
IET10027	Jaladhi/CN644	1 Nov (160)	172	79	3.00	27.3	2.0	7.8
IET10006	Pankaj/Patnai 23	1 Nov (160)	177	101	2.54	26.5	1.9	8.3
IET9071	Purelineselection	28 Oct (156)	185	79	2.91	16.1	1.9	7.8
IET9017	Selection from tall composite	30 Oct (158)	183	64	2.48	29.3	1.6	8.0
IET11184	Waihoku/CR1014	30 Oct (158)	150	81	1.86	19.9	1.5	6.8
Hathipanja (check)	—	26 Oct (154)	163	70	2.51	31.0	1.7	8.0
SE			10	9	0.60	0.5	0.4	1.3

^aDE = days after emergence.

t/ha (see table). Straw yields were much higher than grain yield and did not vary significantly among cultivars.

There was a significantly positive correlation of grain yield with plant height at maturity ($r = 0.771^{**}$) and

panicle weight ($r = 0.842^{**}$). Panicles/m² (considered to be the major yield attribute of medium-duration dwarf varieties under shallow water conditions) did not show any relationship with grain yield ($r = 0.142$ ns).

The results suggest that tall stature and panicle weight types are suitable for deepwater areas where water level increases abruptly. Work is needed to improve panicle numbers for higher productivity. ■

Stability for yield of medium-long-grain rice varieties and advanced lines

F. M. Abassi, M. A. Sagar, and A. Rabbani, Rice and PGR Programmes, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad Pakistan

Cultivars JP5 and DR83 and advanced lines VT1, IR9729-63-3, DR47, Pakhal, and Kunhar were tested over nine locations. Plot size was 5 × 3 m, with 20 cm between and within rows. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 2

seedlings/hill in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-0 NPK kg/ha.

The slope of the regression of genotype mean on site mean yield (bi) is a measure of stability. Pakhal and IR9729-63-3 had slope (0.97 and 1.01, respectively) closest to 1.00 among all genotypes (see table). They also contributed least to genotype × environment interaction, as measured by ecovalence (wi²) and interaction variance (δi²).

In addition, the genotypes had the smallest deviation from regression on the

site index, as measured by the deviation mean square (S²d) of all genotypes. Pakhal was the most stable, followed by IR9729-63-3.

Genotypes DR47, DR83, VT1, and JP5 had regression coefficients greater than 1.0, indicating that they were more responsive under favorable environments and high fertility conditions. Kunhar, with a lower regression coefficient (b < 1.0) seemed suitable for poor environments. These cultivars should be tested across environments for a few years before their release for general cultivation. ■

Stability parameters for grain yield of medium-long-grain rice varieties and advanced lines.

Genotype	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	Mean	Wi	δi	bi	S ² d
VT1	4.6	7560101.39	1175547.81	1.16	710828.10
IR9729-63-3	5.5	4610464.15	659361.30	1.01	394547.70
DR47	4.8	6021657.15	906320.07	1.17	404016.24
Pakhal	4.8	1858478.68	177763.84	0.97	187024.95
Kunhar	5.4	4749940.25	683769.61	0.57	253366.54
DR83	5.3	5719242.00	853397.42	1.27	539474.99
JP5	4.1	4872898.51	705287.31	1.14	484018.75

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.